

PROCEEDINGS OF
THE SEAOHUN 2024
INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE:
ONE HEALTH IN ACTION

18-19 September 2024
Shangri-La Hotel,
Chiang Mai, Thailand

OD-05: BAT GUANO FARMING AND ZOOBOTIC DISEASE RISK REDUCTION IN KANG MEAS DISTRICT, CAMBODIA

Authors: Sok Dou¹, Elizabeth Gold², Marcia Griffiths², Jennifer Peterson³, Elaine Faustman⁴, Tristan Burgess⁵, Katie Limming³, Chanthy Srey¹, Ratana Chhan¹, Sreytouch Vong², Sophal Lorn⁶, Phallin Pan⁷

Institution: ¹Tetra Tech ARD Inc., USAID STOP Spillover, Phnom Penh, Cambodia, ²JSI Research and Training Institute Inc., Arlington, USA, ³Tetra Tech Inc., Pasadena, USA, ⁴University of Washington, Seattle, ⁵Center for Wildlife Studies, Wilcox, ⁶Provincial Department of Agriculture, Kampong Cham Province, ⁷Provincial Department of Rural Development, Kampong Cham Province, Cambodia

Corresponding Author and E-mail: Sok Dou¹, sokdou@gmail.com

Keywords: Bat guano farming communities, Zoonotic diseases, Community-driven risk reduction, Social behavioral change, Spillover risk

Abstract: Bat guano, a valuable fertilizer, can transmit zoonotic diseases to animals and humans. In Cambodia, bat guano farming is a long-standing practice and alphacoronaviruses have been found in bat waste and on household surfaces. This may pose a health risk for bat guano producers (BGPs) and their neighbors (non-bat guano producers, or NBGPs). Women are particularly vulnerable because they do most of the guano collection with limited use of safety measures. The objective of this research was to explore ways that BGPs and NBGPs can protect themselves with feasible and acceptable practices that minimize bat-human contact and safeguard against zoonotic disease transmission. In August 2023, 13 BGPs and 10 NBGPs participated in a three-week “Trials of Improved Practices” (TIPs) implementation. These TIPs introduced and monitored seven community-chosen risk reduction behaviors, during three visits. The first visit assessed existing practices and introduced modifications. Subsequent visits tracked progress and assessed participant experiences, changes implemented, support needed, and family intentions to continue the practices. The BGP and NBGP households demonstrated that with their own resources they can make important changes in biosafety and hygiene practices. The motivating factors were reduced bat waste odor, minimized dust inhalation, and improved family wellbeing. The challenges, however, remained due to limited access to personal protective equipment and some discomfort associated with its use. Participants also expressed commitment to continue these practices due to health benefits and reduced risk of viral transmission. Behavioral change is fundamental to reducing spillover of zoonotic disease from animals to humans. This study highlights the effectiveness of community-driven and tested solutions in mitigating risks related to bat guano farming. By promoting socially, economically, and culturally acceptable risk reduction behaviors, the trials yielded promising results, empowering the bat guano communities to protect themselves from zoonotic disease spillover risks.

SEAOHUN is a leading regional network of universities for One Health capacity building and research.

SEAOHUN NEWSLETTER

To subscribe SEAOHUN's updates on One Health workforce development: <https://www.seaohun.org/newsletter>

info@seaohun.org

www.facebook.com/seaohun

www.seaohun.org

www.instagram.com/seaohun

OUR PARTNERS

USAID
FROM THE AMERICAN PEOPLE

Scan to access
our publication online

